

Table S 1. Summary of bisulphite sequencing data summary.

	IR64				N22			
	Control		Stress		Control		Stress	
	R1	R2	R1	R2	R1	R2	R1	R2
Panicle								
Total read pairs	108775050	108615320	87462910	87410674	116084504	115997922	81779620	81706468
Mapped reads	98474279	98417706	76775560	79792363	113455508	113353608	79621802	79536488
Uniquely mapped reads	65882297	65890725	52166808	52217273	79869245	79918821	55886299	55874636
Mapping efficiency (%)	60.57	60.66	59.64	59.74	68.80	68.90	68.34	68.38
Genome cytosines (Cs)	162152322	162152322	162152322	162152322	162152322	162152322	162152322	162152322
Cs covered	144846011	145082574	144256560	144412461	145775492	146175221	144214688	144561214
Error rate (%)	1.44	1.44	1.44	1.44	1.44	1.44	1.44	1.44
Total methylated Cs	13321653	13321653	11036091	11036091	14526756	14526756	11835387	11835387
Genome coverage	16	16	13	13	20	20	13	13
Flag leaf								
Total read pairs	97366750	97391149	83949520	83895364	28844104	28691648	38330148	38338696
Mapped reads	90264283	90231611	82197466	82133941	24947271	24765250	33938161	33743187
Uniquely mapped reads	60821572	60891261	55933508	55974025	17124076	16985199	23465133	23316183
Mapping efficiency (%)	62.47	62.52	66.63	66.72	59.37	59.20	61.22	60.82
Genome cytosines (Cs)	162152322	162152322	162152322	162152322	162152322	162152322	162152322	162152322
Cs covered	144996348	145259235	144087244	144488960	129399739	129474940	135359399	135379319
Error rate (%)	1.44	1.44	1.44	1.44	1.39	1.39	1.39	1.39
Total methylated Cs	11985025	11985025	11271411	11271411	2365416	2365416	4285371	4285371
Genome coverage	15	15	14	14	4	4	6	6

Table S 2. Summary of methylated cytosines under control and drought stress in IR64 and N22. Value in the bracket indicates the percentage of methylated cytosines out of the total cytosines covered (rounded to first digit).

Treatment	Tissue	Cultivar	Context	Total cytosines covered	Methylated cytosine	Total methylated cytosines	Methylated context out of the total methylated cytosines (%)
Control	Panicle	IR64	CpG	27180898	6417984 (24)	13321653 (9)	48
			CHG	24536211	3867928 (16)		29
			CHH	93128902	3035741 (3)		23
		N22	CpG	27274654	7182106 (26)	14526756 (10)	49
			CHG	24651342	4362850 (18)		30
			CHH	93849496	2981800 (3)		21
	Flag leaf	IR64	CpG	27144702	6125398 (23)	11985025 (8)	51
			CHG	24529960	3579035 (15)		30
			CHH	93321686	2280592 (2)		19
		N22	CpG	24563410	1200561 (5)	2365416 (2)	51
			CHG	22218479	782623 (4)		33
			CHH	82617850	382232 (1)		16
Stress	Panicle	IR64	CpG	26969076	5396594 (20)	11036091 (8)	49
			CHG	24408568	3258908 (13)		30
			CHH	92878916	2380589 (3)		22
		N22	CpG	26951964	5878606 (22)	11835387 (8)	50
			CHG	24405006	3635670 (15)		31
			CHH	92857718	2321111 (2)		20
	Flag leaf	IR64	CpG	26998494	5785983 (21)	11271411 (8)	51
			CHG	24403464	3389949 (14)		30
			CHH	92685286	2095479 (2)		19
		N22	CpG	25545232	2216102 (9)	4285371 (3)	52
			CHG	23125840	1377810 (6)		32
			CHH	86688327	691459 (1)		16

Table S 3. Summary of methylated cytosines overlapped between IR64 and N22 under control condition. Value in the bracket represents percentage of the overlapped cytosines out of the total methylated cytosine for the particular context. mC represents methylated cytosine.

Tissue	CpG	CHG	CHH	Total overlapped mCs	Percentage of overlapped out of the total mCs	
					IR64	N22
Panicle	4880594 (52)	2856086 (31)	1564472 (17)	9301152	70	64
Flag leaf	1005792 (54)	623210 (34)	215639 (12)	1844641	15	78

Table S 4. Summary of overlapped methylated cytosines between flag leaf and seedling data from a previous study (Garg et al., 2015)

Cultivar	Treatment	Total overlapped CpG	CHG	CHH
IR64	control	2314117	1214369	726351
N22	control	2756461	1425271	911403

Table S 5. Summary table of methylated cytosines that overlapped between panicle and flag leaf in IR64 and N22. mC represents methylated cytosine.

Tissue	cultivar	CpG	CHG	CHH	Total overlapped mC
Panicle vs Flag leaf	IR64	5378576	3093660	1520780	9993016
	N22	1184074	749971	246993	2181038

Table S 6. Methylated cytosines found overlapped between control and drought stress.

Tissue	Cultivar	Overlapped mC (Control and drought stress)				Percentage of overlapped mC out of the total mCs found in control (%)
		CpG	CHG	CHH	Total	
Panicle	IR64	4880710	2869784	1597097	9347591	70
	N22	5492595	3283865	1639393	10415853	72
Flag leaf	IR64	5041801	2859964	1336126	9237891	77
	N22	957972	597509	183980	1739461	74

Table S 7. Total number of DI (de-methylated at stress) and DII (denovo methylation at stress) found in IR64 and N22.

Tissue	Cultivar	DI	DII	DII out of the total mC at control (%)	DII out of the total mC at stress (%)
Panicle	IR64	3974062	1688500	30	15
	N22	4110903	1419534	28	12
Flag leaf	IR64	2747134	2033520	23	18
	N22	625955	2545910	26	59

Table S 8. Number of overlapped genes between cultivars that associate with DI (de-methylated cytosines) and DII (denovo methylated cytosines).

Type	Tissue	Expression category	Total gene in IR64	Total gene in N22	Overlapped gene	Genes in N22 overlapped with IR64 (%)
DI	panicle	silent	31057	31397	28753	92
		low	10443	11317	7181	63
		medium	6083	5687	3128	55
		high	6239	5662	4403	78
	flag leaf	silent	30805	24041	22342	93
		low	11258	8073	5529	68
		medium	5721	4125	2303	56
		high	5681	4262	3238	76

DH	panicle	silent	30408	30004	27246	91
		low	10315	10813	6832	63
		medium	6010	5468	2983	54
		high	6157	5371	4157	77
	flag leaf	silent	30318	28570	26133	91
		low	11093	10121	6884	68
		medium	5638	5100	2855	56
		high	5559	5015	3726	74

Table S 9. Drought-induce DMR found in all the tissues of IR64 and N22.

Tissue	Cultivar	context	count	Total DMRs
Panicle	IR64	CpG	940	9929
		CHG	2182	
		CHH	6807	
	N22	CpG	649	9199
		CHG	2803	
		CHH	5747	
Flag leaf	IR64	CpG	738	4639
		CHG	1520	
		CHH	2381	
	N22	CpG	145	673
		CHG	103	
		CHH	425	

Table S 10. Number of DEG whose expressions were negatively correlated with the methylation level of dDMR. dDMR found within 3kb upstream to 3kb downstream regions of gene were considered for this analysis.

Tissue	Cultivar	DMR type	DEG status	Count of DEG
Panicle	IR64	Hyper-DMR	Down-DEG	79
		Hypo-DMR	Up-DEG	36
	N22	Hyper-DMR	Down-DEG	269
		Hypo-DMR	Up-DEG	24
Flag leaf	IR64	Hyper-DMR	Down-DEG	32
		Hypo-DMR	Up-DEG	33
	N22	Hyper-DMR	Down-DEG	1
		Hypo-DMR	Up-DEG	9

